

HONOUR KILLING IN INDIA, A PSYCHO-SOCIAL DISORDER

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ABSTRACT:

The ancient curse of honour killing is still now exists in society, where a person killed by their own family to save the honour of the family, most of honour killings happen during a marriage between different castes, religions and income gaps. Today society subjugates the technology of the 21st century but cannot in terms of caste, class and religion. The discrimination of caste, class, religion and gender, we read in different Epics. The occupation has been selected through the Barna system though today it is totally abolished from society but in the case of marriage, it has existed. The cause of honour killing is a concept of patriarchal society, inter-caste marriage, and khap panchayat as a judicial system where the judicial system is monitored by a leader and his own law and forced to obey. If someone refuses it then he or she will killed according to the leader's order. Besides this suitable income of the groom, lack of proper education, lack of properly enacted law, and teasing/insult by someone are the main causes of honour killing. The paper will analyses the basis of secondary data, here describe some honour killing incidents as examples. The study focuses on the cause and effect of honour killing on society, and how to reduce this type of through changing the mindset of people, though it is very tough but it can be done gradually. It is too time-consuming process, but the study helps to reduce superstition in the human mind.

KEYWORDS:

HONOR KILLING, KHAP PANCHAYAT, CASTE, RELIGION, PATRIARCHY SOCIETY.

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INTRODUCTION

Honour killing is the murder of a person accused of "bringing shame" upon their family. Honour killing is a psycho-social problem In India. It has a broad history from a long year ago to today we all saw that somebody was killed by a close relative like a family member to save the reputation or prestige of the family. In ancient Roman society, honour killing exists where the pater families or senior males within a household right to kill an unmarried but sexually active daughter. Most of the time it was seen that the victim was attacked or killed by his or her family member like brother or father even Mother. Maximum cases are seen in traditional society, where society does not accept the breaking of their traditional prejudice or rules. In Indian patriarchal society, it has often happened with girls. Even in few months ago a student named Indra who touched the drinking pot of a teacher and was beaten. In Manusnhita a Shudra women marry only a Shudra man, she can't not right to marry in a different caste. In the article, some stories are not directly associated with to honour killing but a state of killing like honour killing because to save their prestige they killed them. Honour killing is the murder of a family member by his own family the accusation that the victim brought dishonour to their family. Sometimes it was preplanned by the whole family members they took the revenge to save the family from

disgrace. Mainly in this case women are targeted but in recent times honour killings have not only happened with girls but also boys. But in most of cases, it happened against women. Honour violence coincides with gender violence, in where patriarchal society men are dominated by women all the rules for women are determined by men even in decisions by women. Girls have to no right to their own choice if they do not agree to enter into an arranged marriage or they have a relationship or divorce-separation against their family then they are attacked and sentenced to death by a family member. The honour killing mostly happens in Indigenous societies but so many examples occur in urban societies, the problem of the incident is not only in India but also all over the world, even in highly civilized societies like European countries. People are confused with a psychological problem but it is of social problem or social acceptance. Psychological problem diagnoses and remedies/recovery through counselling but it is not possible social problems. Actually what we think or how we perceive our society or social incident that is the main viewpoint of a person, how they feel and what they feel to society. So now, honour or prestige is how I feel/perceive the society but not how society's people feel/accept.

Though maximum of the various articles focused on

inter-caste, inter-religious, and ter-culture marriage to define the term honour. Most of determined by marriage. But here the writer would like to show on slightly different viewpoints. Honour killing was not a tod's problem, the problem has had to be the forming of human society, when social stratification started and that has still existed killing wevasot an incident of an interfamilial, it was an incident of social stratification, where if a lower class community's person prpractisedn authorized activity (upper class self-proclaimed) and sentenced to death as a punishment. Even we all know that the story Dronacharya and Eklavya in the epic Mahabharata. Drona expected to Eklavya to guru daDakshinand wanted to thumb of his hand as a dakshina, because Drona desire from heart that none can be above Arjun to overcome, because Eklavya was a son of Shudra. So here only the reason Eklavya was a sudhra's son that's why refused and indirect mutilation by guru Dona. In ancient India sati practice was an honour for a society or Hindu religion, it was almost stopped in Mughal era but again it was started after demolish of Mughal period, it w a prevalence in 18th century. Always attacks are not by the own family. In Uttar Pradesh a man took revenge after 15 years of an incident, the cause of taken revenge was the accused family was humiliated by the victims in public.so here the incident was not happened by victim family member but accused was took revenge to family's disgrace.

Committed to suicide is a parallel line of honour killing: We always see the term honour as the tradition or respect of family, but it is ot always. But in the 21st century, honour has been directed to another point of view, which is wealth, land, power, and career or profession. There are a hundred examples or incidents of honour killing that happened only of the bride's wealth as well as her earnings. (As an example, given the most Kolkata-based industrialist daughter Priyanka Todi and Rizwanur Rahman, the Todis family was compelled to commit suicide by humiliating Rizwanur.)

Honour killing: At first, define the term 'honour', then go to killing. Honour is a great esteem, respect, morality, to give special recognition, to regard or admire the reputation of family culture and tradition, religious and castetic superstition. In a narrow sense, preserved virginity of women before marriage is the measure of line of honour; it is a gift of her family as well as dowry to her husband. In so many societies, they decided it was the criteria for an honour. In various cultural or religious communities, they thought that men are rigorous; it does not matter, but women should be loyal and chaste. Even if the society selects their dress code, the girl has no choice or freedom to wear a dress. If someone was generous, we saw in electronic media that the women were killed by the goons, so-called proclaim advisors.

Historical perception: Honour killing is not an incident of the current era. It has a long history all over the world. In ancient Roman societies, sexually active, unmarried women were killed in patriarchal families' rituals. In some parts of the world, raped women are disgraced by a family,

and family members have also been murdered to save the family's dishonor. Honour killings have originated from tribal customs; an allegation can be enough to disgrace a family's reputation, and they believed that without honour, life is not worth living. Most of the honour killings happened in Southeast Asian countries. In India, most honour killing occurred in northern India, where a lot of discrimination existed from man to man, family to family, or society to society. The rest of the country was also seen, but comparatively less. It's main because here the caste system is given great importance. Built up a stigmatising concept of higher-caste people about lower-caste people. Honour was built up in different religious societies. Here, I give an example. In the sense of the sense of Talibani religion, women are born to be slaves; they have no right to access education; they cannot come out of home. Nobel Laureate Malala Yousufzai was attacked by Taliban anti-social activists in 2012. Miss Yousufzai was spreading awareness about educational opportunities and speaking out against how the Taliban's are taking away their right to education. It was dishonourable of the Taliban to educate women, and they took revenge on the leading lady.

Patriarchy society: From the origin of society, not only in India, a male-dominated society was present, but in every country in the world. In the present time, developed countries have abolished this type of stigma, but in developing and underdeveloped countries it is still present. Swami Vivekananda said, "A country developed when we respected the women of society. If we educated more women, the country would be better because an educated mother can educate a family and an educated man can educate one person. In patriarchal society, men play the main role in decision-making. Even now, in the field of politics, men are playing a dominant role. Males are taking decisions in family matters; it seems that girls are homemakers to be born, and they are opposed to any decision of women to grow their heroism or valor. They did not add any value to women. In this society, girls are not allowed to work outside.

Caste/ religious system: Some indigenous caste, i.e tribal system-ingrained ideas like untouchability, are still present. We often saw it prohibited to touch upper caste, even temples for women and shudra caste people. Inter-caste marriage is the main key to honour killing. Most cases of honour killing happen in inter-caste arriages. It is a superstition-rooted concept of traditional rules; it seems that society will lose respect for society, and it is inauspicious.

Endogamy: Endogamy is a marriage practice within groups where people marry their own caste and culture. it has been still now exist some culture, tribal and marginalised community. The endogamy system is an ancestral myth or tale of a society where people don't think marriage can be conducted outside of the community. This thought is still deeply embedded in people's minds, the lies in their traditional beliefs. They cannot marry in other castes; for this, in their society, some bodies marry against their tradition, and then

revenge is born in their minds. The dogma-type people seem to think that breaking tradition is a sin for them.

Primitive Rule: In India, most of the community follows the ancestral tradition; they deeply believe that breaking the rule or tradition of their ancestors will bring them evil or misfortune. Even they think so much that there will always be evil and danger in their family's every time every time because their spirits of their ancestors will be unsatisfied and they will curse.

Statement of the Problem: At present, so many incidents of honour killing happen all over the country just for our ego-centric mind. A family could not accept the choice of their daughter or son in selecting their life partner, so we all think about it peacefully and just take off orthodox values from our minds, put them on another side, and first think deeply that we are all human and there is no discrimination among caste, religion, or class. So accept their choice and let them live peacefully. The researcher is aware and wants a bias-free society to reduce honour killing so that in the future, not a number of people will be killed for the honour of family. So, the researcher stated the problem as "honour killing in India, a psychosocial disorder."

Emergence of the Study: Keep our eyes on news we see lots of incident of honour killing. The incident of honour killing has become a trivial matter to the society. At present it does not make a concern for people's mindset. It has become endure to the society. People don't care about it anymore, for this reason this type of incident increase day by day. So it is the time for concern that's why the researcher focused on this study and try to define it a psyche problem for human, aware to bring out the orthodox root from mind.

Review of related literature:

Kejriwal conducted a study the study entitled 'Honour Killing in North India'. The study was based on secondary data and incident of some honour killing of northern India's were define here, Haryana was rate high in according to percentage of honour killing. The researcher took a survey on 120 people most them claimed on inter-caste marriage, next to inter religious, then financial gaps of family, then the occurrence of crime happen only for same village marriage and a least number of incident based on see another honour crime. Here the researcher shown the main reason of honour killing was low sex ratio.

Preethi & Sreelatha conducted a study the study entitled 'HONOUR KILLING IN INDIA'. The study shows various heinous murdered of saving the honour of family, the study was conduct through collection of secondary data and the study represents that the honour killing treated as usual murdered case but there is no separate provision for it, honour killing mostly happen in northern India where Hariyana Punjab and Uttarpradesh the main reason is orthodox believe of upper caste, the study focused that religion also a prime factor of this crime. The studies described sati system is a part of this type of crime which have legal before though now abolished.

Ahammed Conducted a study, the study entitled 'Honour killing in India: A Psychological analysis'. The study was based on reports, research studies and anecdotes published and observations made with an intensive approach with the help of secondary data, the study follows exploratory research method. The study conduct on the relationship of attitude with emotion and belief and altogether is effected on human behaviour. Here the researcher define two types of emotion one is love another is fear. When fear is defeated to love then victims eloped. When a family is conflict with traditional belief then they consider to family's value and anger came into emotion and after took revenge. The study points out how the multifarious psychological aspects influencing 'honour killing' and to what extent it creates panic and havoc in the society which deter the stability of social life thereby ends life of many citizens in a nation as well as affects the development of a nation.

Objectives of the Study :

- i) To study the consequences of honour killing in Indian society.
- ii) To study the causes of honour killing.
- iii) To study the different cases honour killing
- iv) To reduce honour cases through changing the obdurate superstited conception.

Methodology: The article is based on secondary data collection and analysis of various documentary on honour killing. The study were conduct with the help of various social media platform specially YouTube and Internet.

Cause:

Insult/Teasing: Teasing/bullying is a big issue that we often see in the news because prestige is related to teasing. There are so many incidents related to insult and prestige. An example is explained here according to a TV and newspaper report. A man took revenge after 15 years because the victim humiliated the accused mother and wife in a land dispute, though both victim and accused are neighbors. At that time the accused was silent and left the neighborhood and went to another place, and since then the accused has harbored anger. The cops said when they asked the accused why you took revenge after such a long period, the accused said his son was then a child. The accused knew to the cops that he had decided in mind when his son would be 15 years old, then he took the revenge. The accused man's son turned 15 years old in November, then he murdered the victim in December.

Caste System: The caste system is a tonnes of problem from ancient society; it is the main problem of an honour killing in the overall world. The superstition of this system is deeply rooted in society today. The existence of a caste system is a main curse of society. Generally, the endogamy-matting-rooted idea is the main culprit to conduct an honour killing. Most incidents happen after an inter-caste marriage and refusal to marry family selection. In India, caste systems exist, even gotra systems exist in cultural and literate families. An overall observation

getting from the matrimony site is that there are all profiles of brides, especially in upper caste communities. The basic and main preference must be the same community; even we see they match to subcaste, gon, rashi, etc.

Khap Panchayat: It is not an elected panchayat, this is a community organization which run the clan by socially influenced community, especially in northern part of India,(Uttar Pradesh jat community) actually the body of panchayat is form by a upper caste community, which community are dominated the society previously. and they have enjoy their power by their ancestor rules, they took decision against any constitutional provision, in any problem happen in community the call a meeting, after meeting they imposes punishment to victim, actually they compelled to the people to be victim. They obliged to people to committed to murdered

Prestigious Job or Income: It is an another problem of honour killing is a prestigious job or income.in this cases an established, reputed and rich family's bride elope with a poor family's groom. Then the families of bride want to take revenge on groom's family, this incident we saw in India's society but it is in number very few.

Religious System: There were so many incident of honour killing to conduct a marriage between different religion , where society lead by so called religious guru who are urge the society to ostracized those family where marriage happen.

Male Dominant Society: Indian constitution stated that we are equal before the law, but in rural area before a decade cycle ride of women was prohibited to going to school in a specific religion. In a religious society respectable people of the society used to convince the family of girls for marriage, family who did not accept their proposal they are avoid by whole society, so, they were forced to follow the society.

Not Rigorous Constitutional Provision: The main problem of honour killing is no rigorous law against it. Though in India there are so many law of murder or killing but there is no special law for honour killing, for this reason the bride family feel easy to conduct a murder to save their family's prestige. Though Indian constitutions article 14 and 15 refers we are equal before to law according to caste, creed, sex and religion, article 17 refers abolished untouchability, article19 and 21 right to freedom and life, so a person have right to select life partner no one can interfere in it. Indian penal code defines the punishment for honour killing is not less than seven years it may increase to the severity of incident.

Lack of Education: Education means not only subject knowledge but also changing behavior in progressive manner. But we see everywhere established literate family's marriage system is strictly to same community. We listen so many lecture on seminar, class etc. where resource person are lecture on caste and religious free society but when they practice it in their own life they biased. An example from matrimony sites where a bride's

family willing to marriage her girl and their main preference/ choose has no- other caste please excuse us. So here I want to say a Bengali proverb- you practice first in your own life then teaches others. Here another example of social reformer and Bengali barnaparichoy introducer Iswar Chandra Vidyasagar introduced widow marriage through married a widow woman with her son. So that is called education.

Legislation Frame: India does not have a dedicated law for addressing honour killings. In India, there is no specific legislation on honour killings. These offences will be prosecuted under the relevant sections of the Indian Penal Code (IPC) related to'murder': 299-304 (murder and culpable homicide), 107-11 (abetting murder), and 120A and 120B (criminal conspiracy). Apart from the IPC, incidents of honour killings are also eligible for protection under the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989, which specifically addresses crimes against Dalits and indigenous people. The outcome remains unchanged as 'honour killings' perpetuate pride in the perpetrators for safeguarding the honour of their family, caste, or community. 14th Article of the Indian Constitution ensures equal treatment for all individuals. The legal system and fairness under the law. Engaging in honour killing contradicts this principle. Article 15 states a Constitution that bans prejudice regarding the foundation of race, gender, societal class, and birth location.

Domestic Violence Act, 2005: While its main focus is on domestic violence, this law also offers protection and legal options for victims of honour-based violence in the family.

Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993: This legislation, creating the NHRC, plays a role in tackling human rights abuses, such as honour killings.

State-Specific Laws: Certain states have implemented laws to tackle honour killings. As an example, Haryana and Punjab have put in place particular rules or actions to deal with and stop such offenses.

Supreme Court Guidelines: The Supreme Court of India has issued guidelines to protect individuals at risk and ensure accountability for honour killings.

Prevention: Multiculturalism can eradicate the obdurate concept of honour killing. Multiculturalism is the melting pot of different societies where views of different cultures are mixed up and equal rights. People are civilised and accept various cultures; that's why society comes out of an audacious/overweening attitude. Educating people, especially religious leaders as well as women, to know their basic rights and law against such brutal crimes. Eradicate of colour and caste discrimination can help to reduce to this type of heinous crime. Volunteer organisations and NGO's should take initiative in an awareness program against honour killing.

Conclusion: We all introduced by our civilized society, we all blessed that we got a great constitution, by which we learn every day what we should do or what should not, even the supreme court of India amendment the

constitution through realizing and judgment, article 12 to 35 contained in part III of the constitution deal with fundamental rights. These are right to equality. Freedom, right against exploitation, prohibition of discrimination according to caste, gender and religion, that almost everyone knows, after knowing of all these the incident of honor killing took place, because of orthodox values of ancestral tradition. We considered the values or prestige of family related with women, man are the suprimo of family, so they seems that they are interfere the choosing of life partner of their daughter or son, if a daughter or son marriage against family decision then the family member took revenge.

It is emphasized that honour killing are not justified with any other killing, it is violate basic human rights, freedom of choice and gender equality. So in cases of honor killing there are so many clause were imposed in this cases.

It is challenged to combat honour killing, but govt. should take initiate and enact and enforce new laws that explicitly criminalized and punishment. Negligence of judiciary and police the incident happened more. In some cases eloped couple are feel threatened and they appeal to police protection, even after it some incident happened, so the police and judicial system be more careful about after inter-caste marriage.

It is crucial to promote gender equality, women's empowerment, and respect for individual autonomy. Community leaders, religious institutions, and civil society organizations play a vital role in fostering a culture that values human life, dignity, and human rights.

Ultimately, eradicating honour killings requires a collective effort to address the underlying social, cultural, and systemic factors that contribute to their persistence. By promoting human rights, gender equality, and justice, we can strive to create a world where honour killings are seen as abhorrent and belong to a dark chapter of history, rather than a present-day reality.

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